

Attempts to Synthesise Uric Acid from Nine-membered Cycloids.

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The syntheses of uric acid known at present involve reactions which are many and complex, the starting material itself being not easily obtained in some cases. Horbaczewski's synthesis (*Ber.*, 1882, 15, 2678 ; *Monatsh.*, 1885, 6, 356; 1887, 8, 206) which at present is of interest merely as being the first, was to heat urea with glycocoll or cyanacetic acid; but Hoffmann (*Annalen*, 1925, 441, 215) asserts that "not a trace of uric acid is formed by heating urea with glycocoll".

For all the syntheses of uric acid and purine bases, Behrend and Roosen (*Ber.*, 1881, 21, 999; *Annalen*, 1888, 251, 235), Baeyer and Schlieper (*Annalen*, 1863, 127, 3), Fischer (*Ber.*, 1895, 28, 2473; 1897, 30, 559), Traube (*Ber.*, 1900, 33, 1371, 3035), John (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 41, 58; 1911, 45, 79) have first prepared a 4:5-disubstituted pyrimidine derivative and then built up the iminazole ring from the substituent groups in the 4:5-positions. It, therefore, seemed that if uric acid or any of its more closely allied derivatives could be synthesised from a simple nine-membered cycloid, the suggestion that similar syntheses take place within the living organism from the polypeptides, which are known to be among the degradation products of proteins in the body, would gain probability. Apart from this, any simple synthesis of uric acid or its derivatives would possess an intrinsic interest and also might be useful for the preparation of some of the important purine derivatives occurring in plant products, such as caffeine, theobromine, theophylline, etc. The methods, which have now been tried to achieve this end, differ fundamentally from the earlier syntheses by attempting to bridge a nine-membered cycloid in such a way that the required pyrimidine and iminazole rings come into existence simultaneously, as they exist in the uric acid molecule.

Three distinct methods of attacking the problem were planned. The first was to condense oxalyldiurethane with urea to produce

carbo-oxalyldiurea (I) which on reduction might yield uric acid (II)

(I)

(II)

The possibility of bridge formation on reduction of carbo-oxalyldiurea might now be considered. The removal of the oxygen atoms from positions 2:4, 2:9, 4:6 and 6:8 would lead to the formation of three-membered rings, and from 6:9 a four membered ring which are not likely to be stable and hence their formation improbable. While there is undoubtedly the possibility of the 2:6-linkage, by far the most stable system would result from the linking of the 4:8 carbon atoms (or what amounts to the same thing, between 4:9) giving rise simultaneously to a five and a six-membered ring. It was expected that reduction of carbo-oxalyldiurea would yield a mixture of products (II) and (III).

(II)

(III)

The hydrolysis of oxalyldiurethane to the corresponding diacid was first attempted in the expectation that the latter would be more reactive than the ester, and be condensable with urea in presence of phosphorus oxychloride, analogous to Grimaux's synthesis of malonylurea. Alkalis and acids of various strengths under varying conditions were tried as hydrolysing agents but in every case there was complete disruption of the molecule into carbon dioxide,

ammonia and oxalic acid. Finally carbethoxy-oxamic acid, $\text{CO}_2\text{H}\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{CO}_2\text{Et}$, $3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (IV) was isolated by using hydrochloric acid (1:6) and it is surprising that a compound of such simple structure is now obtained for the first time.

The hydrolysis of oxalyldiurethane to oxalodicarbamic acid having failed, it became necessary to attempt the direct condensation of urea with oxalyldiurethane.

From an equimolecular proportion of oxalyldiurethane and urea heated at $120\text{--}25^\circ$ for eight hours it has been possible to isolate the expected carbo-oxalyldiurea (I), carbethoxyoxamide $\text{CO}_2\text{Et}\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{NH}_2$ (V), dicarbamyloxalyldiurethane (VI), an alkali-soluble white sandy powder (VII, m.p. above 340°), and allophanic ester. Carbethoxyoxamide is evidently formed from oxalyldiurethane by hydrolysis and decarboxylation during the process of isolation of the products.

The compound believed to be dicarbamyloxalyldiurethane (m.p. 230°) would be formed according to the following scheme:

It does not respond to biuret test. On treatment with alkali it yields ammonia, alcohol and sodium oxalate.

The infusible compound (VII) responds to the biuret test and yields ammonia with boiling caustic alkali. Without any further experimental proof it is not possible at this stage to attribute to it any definite structure.

From one molecule of oxalyldiurethane and more than two molecules of urea at a fusion temperature ($135\text{--}40^\circ$) there has been obtained oxalyldibiuret (VIII), besides other products not examined.

In an attempt to prepare oxalyl diurea from oxalyldiurethane and ammonia we have obtained oxalylbiuret (VIIIa) besides the expected diurea, which evidently loses a molecule of ammonia:

A similar attempt to prepare the amide of hydantoic acid, $\text{NH}_2 \cdot \text{CO} \cdot \text{NH} \cdot \text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{CO} \cdot \text{NH}_2$, from urethaneacetic ester by the action of the ammonia resulted in the formation of a monoamide (m.p. 105°), isomeric with hydantoic ester, $\text{NH}_2 \cdot \text{CO} \cdot \text{NH} \cdot \text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{CO}_2\text{Et}$ (m.p. 135°), and having the probable constitution, $\text{CO}_2\text{Et} \cdot \text{NH} \cdot \text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{CO} \cdot \text{NH}_2$.

Direct bridge formation by reduction of the carbonyl groups in position 4:8 or 4:9 of carbo-oxalyldiurea has been tried without success by (a) exposing a mixture of the substance and alcohol in a sealed tube to sunlight (*cf.* *Ber.*, 1900, **33**, 2912), (b) sodium and moist ether (*cf.* Perkin and Kipping, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1891, **59**, 218) and (c) zinc dust and alcoholic potash (*cf.* Beschke, *Annalen*, 1909, **369**, 184), these being mild reduction processes for effecting internal pinacone condensation; more drastic methods of reduction have not been tried, being evidently unsuitable. A promising line of approach will be electrolytic reduction, which has been used successfully for a variety of substances related to the purines (*cf.* Tafel, *Ber.*, 1901, **34**, 258, 1165, 3286; *Ber.*, 1900, **33**, 3383; Knorr and Klotz, *Ber.*, 1886, **19**, 3300; Wollers, *Annalen*, 1902, **324**, 279).

Meanwhile, scarcity of the requisite materials turned our attention to the synthesis of carboethylenediurea (IX) which on dehydration should give desoxyuric acid (X) thus:

It is presumed that the methylene hydrogen in position 8 or 9 would condense with the carbonyl oxygen in position 4 in preference to those in position 2 or 6, the product in either case being desoxyuric acid. Removal of water from the oxygen of the carbonyl groups in position 2 or 6 and hydrogen from 8 or 9 is less likely, as the latter would result in the formation of the unstable three- and four-membered systems. By using boiling concentrated hydrochloric acid, a product supposed to be desoxyuric acid (X) and showing the characteristic properties of uric acid was obtained. This compound is not known, though Tafel (*Ber.*, 1901, 34, 250) suggested its formation as a transient intermediate product during the electrolytic reduction of uric acid into purine.

The third method planned for the synthesis of uric acid was analogous to the synthesis of desoxyuric acid by dehydration of carboglycollyldiurea. The problem, in the first instance, is, therefore, to synthesise glycollyldiurea (XI), which by the action of urea or phenyl carbonate could be converted to carboglycollyldiurea (XII).—

Eppiger (*Beitr. Z. Chem. Physiol. u. Pathol.*, 1905, 6, 287) claims to have obtained glycollyldiurea (m.p. 158°) by the action of sulphuric acid and potassium cyanate upon the amide of hydantoic acid. The original paper being not available, the preparation was tried according to the method available in the abstract (*Chem. Zentr.*, 1905, 1, 947) more than a dozen times under different conditions and with varying quantities of material, but only cyanuric acid could be isolated.

The action of urea upon hydantoic ester or amide and of biuret upon urethaneacetamide or hydantoic ester was next tried in the

hope of obtaining glycollydiurea from the first two reactions and carboglycollydiurea from the third and the fourth.

The first reaction has yielded hydantoin and cyanuric acid together with a very small quantity of a crystalline yellow substance, m. p. 236°, agreeing in composition with the expected glycollydiurea (XI) $\text{C}_4\text{H}_8\text{O}_3\text{N}_4$ and a fourth substance glycollybiuret (XIII) which appears to have been formed from glycollydiurea by the loss of a molecule of ammonia.

(XIII)

The conversion of hydantoic ester and amide into hydantoin by the action of heat, acid and alkali is well known. Hydantoin itself has now been found to react with urea to give a small yield of glycollydiurea in analogy with the formation of oxalydiurea from parabanic acid and urea (Biltz and Topp, *Ber.*, 1913, **46**, 1404;

Grimaux, *Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1879, *ii*, 32, 100; Bornwaler, *Chem. Zentr.*, 1912, **II**, 910, 1739).

The biuret reactions have not yielded the desired product; a yellow crystalline compound (m. p. above 340°, N, 35.71%) has, however, been isolated besides cyanuric acid from the hydantoic ester reaction.

These fusion reactions having proved not very useful for the preparation of carboglycollyldiurea in the workable yield, attempts are being made to produce these substances from carbethoxyglycine chloride of Fischer and Otto (*Ber.*, 1903, 36, 2107), as follows:

The action of urea with carbamidoacetic acid in presence of condensing agents like acetic anhydride, POCl₃, fuming sulphuric acid, etc., is being investigated (*cf. Ber.*, 1900, 33, 1380, 3034; 1908, 41, 530; *Annalen*, 1904, 335, 364) and with hydantoic ester in presence of sodium ethylate (*cf. D. R. P.* 165224, 193446, 158553; *Annalen*, 1905, 340, 336) in the hope of producing satisfactory yield of glycollyldiurea. The result of these investigations will form the subject of a subsequent communication.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Improved method of preparing oxalyldiurethane.—Oxalyldiurethane could not be obtained in a satisfactory yield by the previous methods (Hantzsch, *Ber.*, 1894, 27, 1250; Priestley, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 95, 453; Diels, *Ber.*, 1903, 36, 739). To sodium wire (7.5 g.) suspended in dry benzene (200 c.c.) was added dry powdered urethane (25 g.). The reaction commenced immediately and became quite vigorous after about three quarters of an hour when there was much frothing. The flask was cooled in ice-water and occasionally shaken. After 24 hours ethyl oxalate (43 g.) was added to the sodium urethane for 15 minutes with frequent shaking, the temperature being not allowed to rise above 0° and after about an hour

the flask was allowed to attain the room temperature. The pasty mass, formed on the addition of 4*N*-sulphuric acid (200 c. c.), hardened to a light colourless solid on being cooled with ice. This was filtered at the pump, thoroughly washed with water to remove the last trace of sodium sulphate and then crystallised from about 500 c. c. of 80% alcohol. On standing overnight in an ice-chamber, colourless glistening plates of oxalyldiurethane were deposited, m. p. 172°, yield 23 g.

Hydrolysis of oxalyldiurethane.—Oxalyldiurethane (2 g.) was heated under reflux with potassium hydroxide solution (25 c. c.) of strengths *N*, 2*N* and 4*N*, on a water-bath for periods varying from $\frac{1}{2}$ -3 hours. The clear solution after cooling was neutralised in each case with dilute hydrochloric acid and evaporated to dryness on the water bath. The absolute alcoholic extract of the colourless residue gave on concentration colourless crystals of oxalic acid, m.p. 98°, mixed m. p. remaining undepressed.

Carbethoxyoxamic acid (IV).—Oxalyldiurethane (2 g.) was heated under reflux with 60 c.c. of dilute hydrochloric acid (1:6) for 1½ hours on a water bath with occasional shaking and the solution evaporated to dryness. The colourless solid residue could after various attempts be freed from oxalic acid by repeatedly (8-9 times) washing with anhydrous methyl alcohol. A solution of the residual solid in the minimum quantity of hot water gave on standing for 3-4 hours at 0° colourless crystals, m. p. 133-34°, yield 1 g. The substance is very soluble in water at ordinary temperature and in alcohol, but sparingly soluble in ice-cold water and in methyl alcohol. It is soluble in alkalis and in sodium carbonate. (Found: C, 27.62; H, 6.58; N, 6.28. $C_5H_7O_5N, 3H_2O$ requires C, 27.90; H, 6.11; N, 6.51 per cent).

Oxalyldiurethane and urea.—An intimate mixture of dry oxalyldiurethane (30 g.) and urea (12 g.) was heated at 120-25° for 8 hours with occasional stirring when ammonia was evolved. The molten, pale yellow mass frothed gently and drops of liquid condensed on the sides of the flask. On cooling, the contents became a pale yellow, hard solid which after being well powdered was digested repeatedly with 80% alcohol. The alcoholic extract deposited on cooling a microcrystalline solid (A), the mother liquor (B) being almost colourless.

Allophanic ester.—(A) separated from 10% acetic acid in colourless crystals, m. p. 188-89°, yield 6 g., identified by mixed melting

point and analysis as allophanic ester (Found: N, 21.23; Calc. N, 21.2 per cent).

Carbethoxyoxamide (V).—The mother liquor from allophanic ester on being concentrated to about one quarter its bulk gave a crystalline deposit which after repeated crystallisation from water yielded colourless glistening plates, m.p. 155-56°, yield about 2 g. The substance is fairly soluble in alcohol, sparingly so in water and insoluble in ether. (Found: N, 17.64. $C_5H_8O_4N_2$ requires N, 17.50 per cent).

Carbo-oxalyldiurea (I).—The acetic acid filtrate after the isolation of allophanic ester deposited on concentration lemon-yellow crystals, which after being washed with water was repeatedly crystallised from a small quantity of dilute acetic acid, m. p. above 300°, yield about 5 g. (Found: N, 28.06, 27.92. $C_5H_4O_5N_4$ requires N, 28.01 per cent). It responds to the biuret reaction and on hydrolysis with alkali is readily decomposed into ammonia, carbon dioxide and oxalic acid.

The main portion of the reaction product was a yellow, noncrystalline solid left after alcohol extraction and was purified by precipitating it several times with concentrated hydrochloric acid from its solution in 2N-sodium hydroxide. The precipitation does not appear to be quantitative and takes place slowly on standing. The substance does not melt even at 330°. The purity of the substance was established by the identical analytical values obtained from different samples. (Found: N, 35.47, 35.69. $C_5H_{10}O_5N_6$ requires N, 35.89 per cent).

Dicarbamyloxalyldiurethane (VI).—The alcoholic filtrate (B) when evaporated on a water-bath gave a solid which on being crystallised from water gave as the first crop a small quantity of carbethoxyoxamide (m. p. 155-56°); the subsequent crops on being crystallised together from water gave a white crystalline compound, m.p. 230°. (Found: C, 37.41; H, 4.78; N, 17.31. $C_{10}H_{14}O_8N_4$ requires C, 37.73; H, 4.40; N, 17.81 per cent).

Oxalyldibiuret (VIII).—An intimate mixture of oxalyurethane (8 g., 1 mol.) and dry urea (5 g., more than 2 mols.) was heated at 135-40° for 3½ hours. The powdered melt was extracted with boiling water and the filtrate gave on cooling pale yellow crystals, which were boiled repeatedly with alcohol, finally with water and dried at 110°, m.p. 185-86°, yield about 3 g. (Found: N, 32.68. $C_6H_8O_6N_6$ requires N, 32.31 per cent). It gives the biuret test

and is decomposed by boiling alkali into ammonia, carbon dioxide and oxalic acid.

Oxaldiurethane and ammonia: Formation of oxalyldiurea and oxalylbiuret (VIII a).—The white precipitate separating out from a mixture of oxalyldiurethane (6 g.) and liquor ammonia (50 c.c.) on standing for 48 hours, was crystallised from a large quantity of water, m.p. above 350° , yield 2 g. (Found: N, 32.06. $C_4H_6O_4N_4$ requires N, 32.18 per cent). It is insoluble in ammonia and hence cannot be cyanuric acid (N, 32.56).

The ammoniacal filtrate gave on evaporation a solid mixed with a pasty liquid from which on alcohol treatment a solid separated. It crystallised from alcohol in shining white needles, m.p. 235° . (Found: N, 27.04. $C_4H_3O_4N_3$ requires N, 26.75 per cent). The alcohol containing the paste gave on concentration and cooling a white crystalline solid, m.p. 140° , yield 0.03 g.

Urethaneacetamide.—The clear solution obtained from a mixture of urethaneacetic ester (10 g.) and liquor ammonia (50 c. c.) after standing overnight gave on evaporation a white solid (m.p. $80-90^{\circ}$) which after repeated crystallisation from alcohol-benzene melted sharply at 105° . (Found: N, 19.27, 19.18. $C_5H_{10}O_3N_2$ requires N, 19.18 per cent).

Hydantoic amide and phenyl carbonate: Formation of glycollylbiuret (XIII).—An intimate mixture of hydantoic amide (5 g.) and phenylcarbonate (18 g.) was heated at $170-180^{\circ}$ for 45 minutes, developing the odour of phenol. The unchanged phenyl carbonate and phenol were removed by digesting successively with boiling water and carbon tetrachloride. The residual black tarry mass after being washed with ether was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. $220-21^{\circ}$ (Found: N, 29.67. $C_4H_5O_3N_3$ requires N, 29.37 per cent).

Carboethylenediurea (IX).—To carbodiurethane (50 g., 1 mol.) contained in a 250 c.c. conical flask was added ethylenediamine hydrate (20 g.) and after a few minutes, the carbodiurethane dissolved forming a light orange, viscous solution, which gradually became hot. After about 20 minutes a white solid separated. The contents of the flask were then heated under reflux on a water-bath for about $\frac{1}{2}$ hour, 100 c.c. of water added and then filtered. The residue crystallised from a large quantity of boiling water, m.p. $188-89^{\circ}$, yield 25 g. It was identified as allophanic ester by mixed m.p. and analysis. (Found: N, 21.34. $C_4H_8O_6N_2$ requires N, 21.2 per cent).

The pale yellow filtrate on evaporation on the water-bath left a viscous, light-brown residue which on standing in a vacuum over sulphuric acid for about a fortnight congealed to a jelly-like mass. The latter on being refluxed with methyl alcohol left a white powder which crystallised from a large quantity of water, m.p. 275-76°. The yield was only about 1.5 g. (Found: C, 34.46; H, 5.01; N, 31.67. $C_5H_8O_3N_4$ requires C, 34.88; H, 4.65; N, 32.55 per cent). The experiment was repeated twice. The methyl alcohol used for refluxing the jelly-like solid deposited on standing some unchanged carbodiurethane.

Dehydration of carboethylenediurea: Formation of desoxyuric acid (?) (X).—Carboethylenediurea (3 g.) was heated with concentrated hydrochloric acid (20 c.c.) under reflux on a water-bath for about 2 hours. The white solid obtained from the solution on evaporation was dissolved in the minimum quantity of 2*N*-potassium hydroxide. The filtered solution after acidification with concentrated hydrochloric acid and on being allowed to stand deposited a colourless solid, yield about 0.6 g. (Found: C, 39.25; H, 4.21; N, 36.05. $C_5H_6O_2N_4$ requires C, 38.96; H, 3.89; N, 36.36 per cent). It was a white sandy powder, soluble in alkalis and in concentrated sulphuric acid. It did not melt even at 340°. On heating the substance over a free flame it did not fuse, but gave urea as one of the decomposition products. On attempting the murexide reaction, a pale yellow to orange-red coloration resulted. This is only to be expected since murexide, formed from uric acid, contains the strong chromophore carbonyl, which in the case of the analogous compounds obtained from desoxyuric acid is replaced by the methylene group. It may be pointed out that the methyluric acids give the murexide reaction so long as the -CO- group referred to above is intact and purone does not give any murexide test at all.

Hydantoic ester and urea: Isolation of glycollyldiurea (XI) and glycollylbiuret (XII).—Hydantoic ester was prepared from glycine ester hydrochloride and potassium cyanate according to the method of Haber (*Ber.*, 1900, **33**, 3418). An intimate mixture of hydantoic ester (10 g.) and urea (6 g.) was heated in an oil bath at 130-35° for 6 hours when evolution of ammonia ceased. A hot water extract of the powdered melt gave on cooling a yellowish solid from which hot alcohol extracted a dull yellow substance leaving cyanuric acid undissolved. The yellowish solid on being crystallised twice from the minimum quantity of water was obtained in yellowish plates,

m.p. 236°, yield 0.2 g. (Found: C, 29.6; H, 4.81; N, 35.31. $C_4H_8O_3N_4$ requires C, 30.0; H, 5.00; N, 35.00 per cent).

The filtrate from glycollyldiurea was concentrated to one quarter its bulk from which on cooling there separated a white granular solid, m.p. 215° after crystallisation from alcohol and identified as hydantoin by mixed m.p., yield about 3.5 g.

The original filtrate from hydantoin and the mother liquor obtained during its crystallisation gave a solid on evaporation to dryness which on being repeatedly crystallised from water gave two substances melting respectively at 220-21° and 132°, the latter being urea while the former (yield 0.2 g.) gave the following result on analysis. (Found: N, 29.81. $C_4H_5O_3N_3$ requires N, 29.37 per cent).

Hydantoic amide and urea: Isolation of glycollyldiurea.—The experimental procedure was the same as in the foregoing experiment excepting that hydantoic amide required a longer period (25 hours) of heating. The tarry reaction product was extracted with boiling water, the solution evaporated to dryness and the residue digested with 15 c.c. of alcohol. The filtered alcoholic solution gave on cooling about 0.2 g. of a yellow substance which was purified by crystallising twice from water, m.p. 236°, undepressed on admixture with the product from the foregoing experiment.

Hydantoin and urea: Isolation of glycollyldiurea.—From the melt obtained by heating an intimate mixture of hydantoin (5 g.) and urea (4 g.) only 0.8 g. of the yellow crystalline substance (m.p. 236°) could be obtained.